

Principles and applications of cyclic ion mobility

Introduction

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Ion mobility (IMS)
Ion mobility – mass spectrometry (IMS-MS or IM-MS)

Introduction, basic principles

Cyclic TWIMS-Mass Spectrometry System

Operational modes

Selected applications

Conclusion

Principle of ion mobility separation

Ion mobility

$$v_d = K E$$

$$K = \frac{v_d}{E} = \frac{L}{t_d E}$$

v_d – drift velocity of ion, K – mobility, E – electric field intensity,
 t_d – drift time, L - distance

Ion mobility

$$K = \frac{3q}{16N} \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{k_B T}} \sqrt{\frac{m+M}{mM}} \frac{1}{\Omega}$$

Mason-Schamp equation

q – ion charge, N – gas number density (drift/buffer gas),
 m – mass of buffer gas, M – mass of ion,
 k_B – Boltzmann's constant,
 T – absolute temperature, Ω - collision cross-section

$$K_0 = K \left(\frac{N_0}{N} \right) = K \left(\frac{T_0}{T} \right) \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right) = K \left(\frac{273}{T} \right) \left(\frac{p}{1013} \right)$$

K_0 – „reduced“ mobility,
 $N_0 = 2.687 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-3}$, $T_0 = 273.15 \text{ K}$, $p_0 = 1013.25 \text{ hPa}$

„Low-field“: $K = \text{const.}$;
„High-field“: K depends on E/N

Major IMS-MS regimes (commercially available)

DTIMS

TWIMS

TIMS

FAIMS

E direction

E/waveform

Ion motion

Time-dispersive

Ion trapping and selective release

Space-dispersive

Ion mobility – mass spectrometry (IMS-MS)

Why IMS-MS?

Partly complementary techniques (z , m , Ω).

Ion mobility spectrometry provides:

- reduction of chemical noise
- separation of ions into families
- separation of isomers, isobars, conformers
- collision cross-section as other identifier

Buffer gas influence

IMS-MS of Lamotrigine and Rosiglitazone $[M+H]^+$ ions

M.D. Howdle, C. Eckers, A.M.-F. Laures, C.S. Creaser,

Int. J. Mass Spectrom. 289 (2010) 72.

Buffer gas influence

solution

ESI

O-protonated

N-protonated

+

Helium

Nitrogen

IMS benzocaine protomers

S. Warnke, J. Seo, J. Boschmans, F. Sobott, J.H. Scrivens, C. Bleiholder, M.T. Bowers, S. Gewinner, W. Schöllkopf, K. Pagel, G. von Helden, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **137** (2015) 4236;
V. Gabelica, E. Marklund, *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **42** (2018) 51.

Ion mobility spectrometry

Resolving power

Collision cross section: $\Omega/\Delta\Omega$

Drift time: $t_d/\Delta t_d$

Compensation voltage: $C_v/\Delta C_v$

$\Delta \sim \text{FWHM}$

High- > 80; ultra-high- > 200

$z = 1; \Omega/\Delta\Omega$

DTIMS (atm. p 250, low p 140, cyclotron 1040)

TWIMS (SLIM 1860, cyclic 550, > 700), TIMS (400)

FAIMS/DMS ($z = 4, C_v/\Delta C_v, 460$)

Resolving power

DTIMS vs TWIMS

A.T. Kirk, A. Bohnhorst, C.-R. Raddatz, M. Allers, S. Zimmermann,
Anal. Bioanal. Chem. 411 (2019) 6229-6246.

**CCS difference
and
resolving power
selected
examples**

J.N. Dodds, J.C. May,
J.A. McLean,
Anal. Chem. 89 (2017)
12176.

DTIMS: Ion cyclotron mobility (cyclical drift tube)

Cyclic DTIMS

10+3/4 cycles
total path length ~ 20.75 m
resolving power > 300 ($z=2$, $t_d/\Delta t_d$)

S. I. Merenbloom, R. S. Glaskin, Z. B. Henson, D. E. Clemmer,
Anal. Chem. 81 (2009) 1482-1487.

J.C. May, J.A. McLean, Anal. Chem. 87 (2015) 1422-1436.

DTIMS:

Ion cyclotron mobility (cyclical drift tube)

2013 - the first reported
resolving power > 1000
100+3/4 cycles,
~ 180 m,
several seconds
substance P:
[M + 3H]³⁺

R.S. Glaskin, M.A. Ewing, D.E.
Clemmer, *Anal. Chem.* 85
(2013) 7003-7008.

Cyclic TWIMS

Cyclic TWIMS

pass-through

selection
for transit

Design of SELECT SERIES Cyclic IMS

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge,
M. Green, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Design of SELECT SERIES Cyclic IMS

Cyclic TWIMS

$$R \sim \left(\frac{LEQ}{T} \right)^{1/2}$$

R – resolving power, **L** – path length, **E** – applied electric field, **Q** – charge of the ion, **T** – temperature of the buffer gas

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle,
K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green,
Anal. Chem. 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS – Array Electrodes

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green, *Anal. Chem.* 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS

Array Electrodes

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose,
S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D.
Langridge, M. Green, *Anal.*
Chem. 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS

100 passes (98 m); resolving power 750 ($\Omega/\Delta\Omega$)

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green,
Anal. Chem. 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS

Transmission vs passes

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green,
Anal. Chem. 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS: "Wrap around" effect

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green,
Anal. Chem. 91 (2019) 8564-8573.

Trisaccharide mix

Single pass mode

Single pass

Single pass

TOF MS ES+
527.169
7.03e4

Multi-pass mode (scalable IMS resolution)

Multi-pass acquisition

Single pass

Three passes

Five passes

Melezitose (1), raffinose (2), maltotriose (3).

IMSⁿ – ‘Slicing’

IMSⁿ –“Slicing”

Melezitose is ejected, raffinose and maltotriose are ejected to the pre-store, reinjected and then separated by 5 passes

Cyclic TWIMS

Isomeric pentasaccharides:

(I) cellopentaose, (II) maltopentaose, (III) branched mannopentaose

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green, *Anal. Chem.* **91** (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS

product ions from the separated precursors, 6 passes

Maltopentaose, further 14 passes selectively ejected to the store and subjected to CID (200 eV) on reinjection

K. Giles, J. Ujma, J. Wildgoose, S. Pringle, K. Richardson, D. Langridge, M. Green, *Anal. Chem.* **91** (2019) 8564-8573.

Cyclic TWIMS: Application toward petroleum

vacuum gas oil
+ESI

C.P. Rueger, J. Le Maitre,
J. Maillard, E. Riches,
M. Palmer, C. Afonso,
P. Giusti, *Anal. Chem.* **93**
(2021) 5872-5881.

Cyclic TWIMS: Application toward petroleum

C.P. Rueger, J. Le Maitre, J. Maillard, E. Riches, M. Palmer, C. Afonso, P. Giusti,
Anal. Chem. 93 (2021) 5872-5881.

Cyclic TWIMS: LESA Q-cIM-TOF of intact proteins from thin tissue sections

E.K. Sisley, J. Ujma, M. Palmer, K. Giles, F.A. Fernandez-Lima, H.J. Cooper,
Anal. Chem. 92 (2020) 6321-6326.

Cyclic TWIMS: LESA Q-cIM-TOF of intact proteins from thin tissue sections

(A)

(B)

Number of Proteins Detected

E.K. Sisley, J. Ujma, M. Palmer, K. Giles, F.A. Fernandez-Lima, H.J. Cooper, *Anal. Chem.* **92** (2020) 6321-6326.

Cyclic TWIMS: Evaluating the enantiomeric composition

D.A. Cooper-Shepherd, H.J. Olivos, Z. Wu, M.E. Palmer,
Anal. Chem. 94 (2022) 8441-8448.

Cyclic TWIMS: Evaluating the enantiomeric composition

SELECT SERIES Cyclic IMS

Waters

3rd installation
December 2019

Synthetic cathinones

(“plant feeder”, “bath salt”, “charge powder”, “research chemical”)

J. Soares, V.M. Costa, M.d.L. Bastos, F. Carvalho, J.P. Capela,
Arch. Toxicol. 95 (2021) 2895-2940.

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones/phenylethylamine

**3-fluoromethcathinone
(3-FMC)**

**1,3-benzo-
dioxolylbutanamine
(BDB)**

**3-methyl-
methcathinone
(3-MMC)**

Flephedrone

Methedrone

Buphedrone

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

1 pass

5 passes

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

10 passes

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

Mixture of 3-MMC and buphedrone

$[M+Na]^+$

$[M+Li]^+$

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

Cyclic TWIMS: Isomeric synthetic cathinones

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

Alzheimer's disease tau

IMS - 10 pass

pT217
pS214
pT212
brain extract

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

$[M+3H]^{3+}$ (m/z 500.92)

(A)

1 pass

(B)

5 passes

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

m/z 677 generated by CID in trap from $[M+3H]^{3+}$

Separation of Isomeric Tau Phosphopeptides from Alzheimer's Disease Brain by Cyclic Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

mixture of the standards
in molar ratio 1:1:1

Alzheimer's disease brain extract

Probing D- and L-Adrenaline Binding to β 2-Adrenoreceptor Peptide Motifs by Gas-Phase Photodissociation Cross-Linking and Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

Table 1. Relative Energies and Collision Cross Sections of $(\text{SL}^* + \text{H})^+$ Complexes

complex	relative energy ^{a,b}		collision cross section ^c	
	ΔH_0	ΔG_{310}^d	N ₂	He
SL*1	11	0.0	365	253
SL*2	13	2.3	368	254
SL*3	0.1	3.5	345	246
SL*4	2.5	4.1	337	237
SL*5	11	5.6	361	254
SL*6	21	15	362	254
SL*7	30	24	363	255
SL*8	31	26	350	245
SL*9	31	22	356	245
SL*10	33	14	377	261
SL*11	43	30	379	265
SL*12	46	28	368	258
SL*13	49	24	359	252

Y. Liu, Y. Liu, M. Nytko, S. R. Huang, K. Lemr, F. Tureček, J. Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom. **32** (2021) 1041–1052.

Probing D- and L-Adrenaline Binding to β 2-Adrenoreceptor Peptide Motifs by Gas-Phase Photodissociation Cross-Linking and Ion Mobility Mass Spectrometry

SL*1⁺

(0.0 kJ mol⁻¹, 364 Å²)

SL*2⁺

(2.3 kJ mol⁻¹, 368 Å²)

SL*3⁺

(3.5 kJ mol⁻¹, 345 Å²)

SL*4⁺

(4.1 kJ mol⁻¹, 337 Å²)

Y. Liu, Y. Liu, M.
Nytka, S. R. Huang,
K. Lemr, F. Tureček,
J. Am. Soc. Mass
Spectrom. 32 (2021)
1041–1052.

Conclusions

resolving power x duty cycle x ion transmission

Ion mobility with high resolving power

- ✓ improves separation
- ✓ increases the selectivity of IMS-MS
- ✓ widens the applicability of IMS-MS (IMS)
(abused drugs, lipids, proteins, etc.;
characterization of enantiomeric mixtures)

but it has to be considered

- ✓ ion transmission and duty cycle
- ✓ ionization efficiency and matrix effects
- ✓ the influence of conformers, different charge localization
(e.g., protomers) on separation

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